

Lumen

eOSC

Deliverable 8.2

Communication and Dissemination Plan

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List of Acronyms

B-T-S	Base-Target-Stretch
D	Deliverable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EVERSE	European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
EOSC-HE	EOSC-Horizon Europe
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GRAPHIA	Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for Research and Development in Social Sciences and Humanities
IPL	Innovation Prototyping Labs
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Experience
LUMIS	LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics
QR	Quick Response
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SDC	Scientific Domain Committee
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
T	Task
WG	Working group

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the communication and dissemination plan of the LUMEN project. The introductory part of the deliverable drafts the objectives of the communication and dissemination activities as well as the project's primary stakeholders and target audience (chapters 2 and 3).

In chapter 4, "Communication and Dissemination Strategy", the overall approach of LUMEN's communication and dissemination strategy is outlined. The core of LUMEN communication and dissemination activities serves two purposes: raising awareness for LUMEN and showcasing LUMEN outcomes and activities. The chapter elaborates on the technical vision that is key to understanding LUMEN outputs. The LUMEN communication and dissemination strategy therefore feeds from the technical vision. The chapter further dives into the four communication phases that mirror the development phases of the project: 1) Bootstrapping Phase, 2) Consolidation Phase, 3) Adoption Phase, and 4) Delivery Phase. Subchapter 4.3 lays out how LUMEN adopts a cross-domain approach by engaging diverse scientific communities. Subchapters 4.4 and 4.5 further explain how collaboration with projects like GRAPHIA and participation in the EOSC-HE working group strengthen cross-project communication and how outreach events and stakeholder engagement are coordinated through dedicated tasks (Ts) to amplify the project's reach and ensure alignment with community needs across Europe.

Subsequently, chapter 5, "Communication Channels", gives a comprehensive overview of the communication channels used by the LUMEN communication team.

Chapter 6 "Communication Campaigns" describes the overall approach to communication campaigns. In more detail, the chapter describes particular communication campaigns dedicated to highlighting LUMEN outputs to launch in the second half of 2025.

Lastly, chapter 7 lays out the monitoring and evaluation framework for the project's communication and dissemination activities, focusing on feedback from LUMEN-organised events and key performance indicators (KPIs).

2. Objectives

D8.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan aims to fulfil three objectives:

1) **Outline a communication and dissemination strategy for the LUMEN project.**

This deliverable outlines the overall communication and dissemination strategy of the LUMEN project as well as communication and dissemination activities planned within the framework of that strategy. This entails a stakeholder analysis that builds upon the stakeholder analysis contained in the Grant Agreement, thereby enabling the communication and dissemination activities carried out through all LUMEN partners to follow a

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stakeholder-tailored approach. The strategy outlined in this document focuses on cross-domain communication.

- 2) **Outline communication and dissemination activities for the LUMEN project.** Furthermore, this deliverable describes a plan for communication and dissemination activities, ensuring that the shape these activities take aligns with the overall communication and dissemination strategy.
- 3) **Provide a framework for evaluating the communication and dissemination activities of the LUMEN project.** Lastly, this deliverable aims to provide a monitoring framework for the communication and dissemination activities that have been carried out. This ensures the continuous evaluation of these activities, thereby facilitating timely improvements and informed decision-making.

3. LUMEN Stakeholder and Target Audience

Identifying the target audience is an important step in ensuring the successful communication and exploitation of the LUMEN project and its outcomes. Once these are identified, the project needs to maintain their engagement, keeping them informed and interested in the project's progress. For this purpose, ten stakeholder groups have been recognised as central to the project:

Stakeholder Category	Contribution to LUMEN	Benefit from LUMEN	Main Communication/Engagement Channels
Individual Researchers	provide usage data, profile data, feedback	enhanced and simplified access to research, increased visibility	Project Website, Social Media, Events, Newsletter, Partner's networks
Research Communities	provide feedback, usage data	enhanced possibilities for collaboration among research communities, faster and simplified uptake of research results	Project Website, Social Media, Events, Newsletter, Partner's networks
Research Infrastructures (RIs)	provide usage data, project data, profile data, feedback, technical support	improved access to research data	Project Website, Events, Partner's networks
Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	financial contributions	improved access to research data, trusted	Project Website, Events, Partner's

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		data	networks
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	provide usage data, profile data, project data, feedback, technical support	research data, dissemination support	Project Website, Events, Partner's networks
EOSC	enhanced discoverability and accessibility through EOSC Exchange, synergies with EOSC-related projects	enrichment of EOSC ecosystem of services, EOSC innovation centre, alignment with EOSC related projects	Project Website, Social Media, (EOSC) Events, Partner's networks,
Data providers	data, feedback concerning the data	improved (meta)data quality and FAIRness, software platform for data providers to present analyses on the quality and FAIR compliance of their data sources	Project Website, Social Media, Events, Newsletter, Partner's networks
Policymakers	funding, usage data	access to experts, trusted data, increased trust in science	Project Website, Events, Partner's networks
Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and private companies	revenue source	access to experts, trusted data	Project Website, Social Media, Events, Partner's networks
Media (Science journalists)	usage data	usage data, multiplier channel	Project Website, Social Media, Events, Newsletter, Partner's networks
Citizens (Citizen Scientists)	usage data	trusted data	Project Website, Social Media, Events, Newsletter

Table 1: LUMEN stakeholders

Building on this foundation, WP8 has established a stakeholder registry aimed at identifying key individuals, organisations, and companies relevant to LUMEN. This registry plays a critical role in supporting the project's community-building and engagement activities. Considerable effort has been made to include representatives from all four scientific domains within the consortium, ensuring that all targeted scientific communities are meaningfully represented. To this end, WP8 collaborated closely with all project partners during the development of the stakeholder registry. This collaborative and interdisciplinary approach will help to align the registry with

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the specific needs and priorities of the diverse scientific domains addressed by the project. The stakeholder registry is designed as a living document, which will be continuously updated throughout the project to reflect newly identified stakeholders.

Following the creation of the stakeholder registry, the identified stakeholders will be mapped to specific engagement actions. This will help to identify opportunities to strengthen relationships with stakeholders. The engagement mapping will be conducted through T8.5 to ensure stakeholder engagement in all four of the targeted scientific domains.

4. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

4.1. Overall Concept

4.1.1. Purpose

The communication and dissemination strategy of LUMEN builds on the brand identity and guidelines laid out in [D8.1 “Communication Kit”](#)¹. The overall concept of the LUMEN communication strategy revolves around two central pillars: 1) Raising awareness for LUMEN and 2) highlighting LUMEN outcomes and activities.

1) Raising awareness for LUMEN

Activities primarily carried out to raise awareness for the project LUMEN aim to introduce the project to a broader audience and enhance its visibility among its target audiences. Campaigns dedicated to raising awareness may include presenting the project’s mission, vision, goals, introducing project partners and their role, as well as showcasing the connection between LUMEN activities and the four scientific domains directly involved in the project. These scientific domains are: Mathematics, Earth System Science, Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and Molecular Dynamics.

All awareness-raising activities in LUMEN draw from the project identity as described in LUMEN [D8.1 Communication Kit](#) (Arasteh-Roodsary, Foumany 2025) and, thereby, strive for continuous and coherent project branding. Naturally, activities serving the first of the two objectives act as a foundation for activities primarily related to purpose 2.

2) Showcase LUMEN Outcomes & Activities

Communication and dissemination activities related to LUMEN’s outcomes and efforts aim to showcase the project’s key results, outputs, and ongoing work. These activities are dedicated to helping increase the impact of the project results and fostering engagement with them in all four scientific communities.

¹ Arasteh-Roodsary, S. L., & Foumany, L. (2025). *LUMEN Deliverable 8.1: Communication Kit*. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15649403>.

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4.1.2 Technical Vision

The core of the project's communication and dissemination strategy is LUMEN's technical vision, which underpins all of its outputs. LUMEN's technical vision begins with a simple yet critical observation: today's research data is not lacking in volume, it's lacking in connection. Across domains, scientific communities have built powerful platforms and amassed vast resources, yet these remain fragmented, siloed, and difficult to align beyond their original context. This disconnect limits interdisciplinary collaboration, weakens the impact of FAIR principles, and slows down scientific discovery.

LUMEN proposes a new model. Instead of adding another centralised platform, it introduces a **federated data mesh architecture** tailored to the scientific landscape, as outlined in the [LUMEN Data Mesh Architecture Framework \(D4.1\)](#). Its objective is not to replace existing infrastructures, but to connect them, aligning their outputs through a shared framework that respects disciplinary autonomy while enabling meaningful interoperability.

This vision is brought to life through a coherent and extensible set of modular components. These include community-specific discovery platforms that expose structured outputs in line with EOSC standards; a semantic infrastructure (LUMIS) supporting cross-domain metadata, vocabularies, and ontologies; FAIR-by-design data products governed by explicit contracts; and a growing suite of shared components that support discovery, navigation, and reuse across disciplines. Together, they enable a distributed yet interoperable ecosystem, where data remains locally governed but globally actionable.

For communication and dissemination, this architecture offers a strong foundation. It transforms what could be an abstract technical vision into a concrete and mobilising narrative, one that resonates with diverse audiences:

- For researchers, it means enhanced visibility and discoverability of their outputs within and beyond their field.
- For infrastructures and data providers, it demonstrates how their existing assets can gain wider impact without being absorbed into a monolithic system.
- For EOSC stakeholders, it offers a tangible example of decentralised alignment, a model that advances Open Science through governance, not centralisation.

By structuring dissemination efforts around this vision, LUMEN can communicate not only the technical components being developed, but also the value they unlock: **enabling collaboration across disciplines, supporting interoperability without forcing uniformity, and making FAIR practices actionable in real research contexts.**

As the project progresses through its communication phases, from bootstrapping awareness to scaling adoption, each milestone in the architecture becomes an

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opportunity to engage. The launch of a new discovery portal, the deployment of a domain-wide data contract, or the rollout of cross-domain search interfaces all provide focal points for campaigns, storytelling, and strategic alignment with the broader EOSC ecosystem.

In short, LUMEN's technical vision is more than an infrastructure blueprint. It provides a concrete foundation for communication and dissemination by clarifying how LUMEN addresses real alignment challenges across disciplines. Rather than promoting abstract ideals, it demonstrates how interoperability, trust, and reuse can be operationalised through tools and governance models that communities can engage with directly.

4.1.3 Communication Phases

LUMEN has four communication phases that mirror the development phases of the project: 1) Bootstrapping Phase, 2) Consolidation Phase, 3) Adoption Phase, and 4) Delivery Phase.

Fig. 1: Communication & Dissemination Phases

1) The **bootstrapping phase** is scheduled for M1 to M12. The communication and dissemination activities of this phase correspond to the research on user needs and the initial development of the LUMEN KERs, raising awareness for the project itself. Throughout this phase, the consortium actively works to raise awareness among key stakeholders through initial communication campaigns, leveraging partners' networks and developing a concept for cross-domain community engagement. Dedicated communication activities, e.g. specific campaigns (see chapter 6), support building the foundation for strong stakeholder engagement.

2) The **consolidation phase** will run from M6-M24. Overlapping with the bootstrapping phase, this phase builds upon the initial stakeholder engagement. Communication and dissemination activities of this phase will exploit early project results to strengthen engagement.

3) The **adoption phase** will run from M18-M36. Communication and dissemination activities during this phase will focus on increasing the use and adoption of some of the LUMEN services and outcomes, facilitating the uptake of project results.

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4) The **delivery phase**, scheduled for M30-36, aims to enhance the exploitation of project results to maximise impact, with KERs at the centre of communication and dissemination activities.

4.2. Cross-domain Approach

A key focus of the project is to utilise the diverse scientific communities present to maximise the impact and enrich the development of the service from diverse angles. Internally, the project has established communication channels with the 4 scientific domains represented in LUMEN.

The communities meet regularly within the Scientific Domain Committee (SDC). In the SDC, each community presents needs and updates on their interaction with the project. That space is leveraged to ensure all are aware of the possibility of shaping and influencing future activities in the project. The goal remains to respect the diversity and uniqueness of each community and how they converge. This ensures all communities have a voice in the discussion around the development of LUMEN.

Each scientific domain has different needs in terms of services. It is therefore important that LUMEN identifies several stakeholders in multiple countries through the stakeholder registry (see chapter 3) and engages them, either during its development phase or even after the end of the project. All communities produced stakeholder lists ranging from research infrastructures, data repositories, data providers, SMEs, research communities and other types. Therefore, in collaboration with the SDC, particularly T8.5, which is dedicated to cross-domain community engagement, will use the stakeholder registry to outline activities around LUMEN outputs that cater to the needs of the respective communities.

This community-sensitive approach aligns with the co-design approach of the project: it enables LUMEN to engage directly with potential users, ensuring their needs are addressed while also fostering a cross-domain community.

4.3. Cross-project Collaboration

LUMEN participates in the EOSC-HE communication and engagement working group (WG). The working group aims to strengthen alignment among involved projects, foster collaboration and pool expertise around communication, dissemination and engagement activities. Through this WG LUMEN leverages the partner projects' channels and expertise for communication and dissemination activities. The podcast "Inside EOSC" (see chapter 4.5) will further enhance bonds with other EOSC projects by touching upon EOSC-transversal topics. A first collaboration with the [EVERSE project](#) is already underway in this context.

Additionally, LUMEN collaborates closely with the GRAPHIA project. A dedicated Mattermost channel has been established for the communication leads of the LUMEN and GRAPHIA projects to ensure ongoing updates and facilitate deeper alignment between both projects. Currently, the first of three Innovation Prototyping

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Labs (IPL) to be held during the lifespan of both projects is being developed collaboratively and is scheduled to take place from October 1–3 in Croatia. With its focus on the SSH, the collaboration with GRAPHIA will be further leveraged to enhance the involvement of the SSH community.

4.4. Outreach Events

Outreach Events are a core component of LUMEN's engagement activities. The term outreach events describes all events that enable consortium members to actively engage with relevant stakeholders. Outreach events may be events organised within the framework of LUMEN or a third-party event.

To ensure coverage of all four scientific domains, T8.4 "Outreach Events" is dedicated to coordinating outreach events and tracking partners' participation in these events. Throughout the project, via T8.4, a workflow for LUMEN-organised outreach events has been developed to help partners organise and ensure timely alignment of communication and dissemination activities.

4.5. Podcast "Inside EOSC"

LUMEN is currently preparing the podcast "Inside EOSC". The podcast will explore the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and thereby serve as a platform to further strengthen the connection and alignment between LUMEN outputs and EOSC activities. Launching in August 2025, podcast episodes will be released monthly.

5. Communication Channels

During the first six months of the project, the main communication channels of LUMEN have been established:

5.1. Website & Blog

The project website serves as the central node for all information on LUMEN. The website gives an overview of the project's objectives, partners and governance. All project outputs are available through it. Additionally, the website features a "News" and an "Events" section that displays all information about important project updates and relevant project-organised events.

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Fig. 2: Screenshot of LUMEN Homepage

The LUMEN Blog serves as a space to publish pieces that highlight specific aspects of the LUMEN project, including presentations of the project partners, event reports, or digestible and lightweight versions of project outputs. Thereby, the LUMEN Blog facilitates access to LUMEN outputs and understanding of its objectives.

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Fig. 3: Screenshot LUMEN Blog

5.2. Social Media

WP8 manages two social media accounts on behalf of LUMEN. The LUMEN LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/lumen-eu>) and the LUMEN Bluesky Account (@lumen-eu.bsky.social). The initial plan was to open a LinkedIn and an X account. However, with the recent political developments and the surge of research community members switching to Bluesky², the consortium opted to open a Bluesky account instead of an X account.

Both accounts serve as a channel to directly engage with what will become the LUMEN community, as well as a means of outreach that serves as a gateway to the project website and, therefore, project outputs.

Fig. 4: Screenshot LUMEN Bluesky Account

² Biever, C. (2025, January 24). *Bluesky's science takeover: 70% of Nature poll respondents use platform*. *Nature*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-025-00177-1>.

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Fig.5: Screenshot LUMEN LinkedIn Profile

5.3. LUMEN Newsletter

The LUMEN newsletter is managed through Mailchimp. Subscription is possible through the LUMEN website. A QR code has been generated for easier promotion of the project newsletter, e.g. at project presentations. Through the newsletter, subscribers will be informed about major project news, events and opportunities to engage in LUMEN.

5.4. Partner's Networks

Communication and dissemination activities carried out will also leverage the network of consortium partners. Particularly in the bootstrapping phase, this will be crucial to ensure the engagement of all four scientific domains (see chapter 4.4 Cross-domain approach).

6. Communication Campaigns

As part of the LUMEN project's communication strategy, WP8 established a dedicated task force for communication campaigns with monthly meetings. This group functions as a central node for planning and coordinating all upcoming communication campaigns across the project. The task force is open to all project partners from all work packages (WPs), providing a space to exchange ideas and shape campaign concepts. Depending on current needs and priorities, meetings may either cover multiple topics or focus on a single campaign. These regular sessions are occasionally complemented by campaign-specific meetings. The structured and collaborative approach ensures alignment across partners and enables consistent communication throughout the duration of the LUMEN project.

The task force is currently planning a series of campaigns around the two central objectives of all LUMEN communication and dissemination activities: 1) Raising awareness for LUMEN and 2) highlighting LUMEN outcomes and activities (see chapter 4.1.1). Campaigns currently in planning cover the following LUMEN outputs activities:

- the LUMEN Data Mesh, to highlight the central technical framework of the project and set the stage for other LUMEN outcomes conceptually connected to the Data Mesh;
- the White-Label Platform, the discovery solution developed by LUMEN that will be adaptable for all scientific communities;
- the co-design process led by WP3, to put a spotlight on the community-led development approach of LUMEN.

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7. Monitoring and Evaluation

To evaluate the impact of communication and dissemination activities carried out, a monitoring and evaluation routine has been established. This routine relies on community feedback, as well as the metrics described in Subchapter 7.2, “KPIs”.

At the end of M6, M18, and M36, the metrics explained below will be evaluated, and, if needed, the communication and dissemination activities, as well as the communication and dissemination strategy, will be modified appropriately.

7.1. Events

For LUMEN-organised events, feedback will be collected from participants through a form at the end of the event. This form evaluates aspects such as the overall satisfaction with the event, how inclined participants felt to engage and which parts of the event were particularly useful to them.

7.2. KPIs

The KPIs used to measure the effectiveness of LUMEN communication and dissemination measures are displayed in the table below. They have been evaluated in M6 and will be evaluated again in M18 and M36. All communication and dissemination KPIs are defined in a Base-Target-Stretch³ approach.

Measure	KPI	B - T - S	M6
Social Media	[LinkedIn & Bluesky]		
	#Posts	200 - 400 - 550	31
	#Followers	640 - 990 -1300	234
Project website	#Visits	2500 - 4500 - 6500	720
Newsletter	#Newsletters sent out	8 - 13 - 18	1

³ The base is the minimum acceptable level of performance, the target is the expected or standard goal, and the stretch represents an ambitious goal.

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Project results made available	#Zenodo Views	2000-4000-7000	159
	# Zenodo Downloads	1000-2000-3000	147
Third-party events; presentation of LUMEN outputs at community events, conferences and webinars	#participation by consortium partners in events (e.g. presentation, talks, panel sessions)	35-55-65	2
White Label Platform promotion events	#participants (in total)	50-70-100	n.a.
LUMEN conference, pitching project results to all stakeholders	#participants	100 - 200 - 250	n.a.
Publishing scientific articles to disseminate & establish engagement with project results	#scientific publications	7 - 12 -16	0
co-design workshops	#co-design workshops	3 - 5 -7	n.a.
Engagement Events training communities, gathering info from communities, enabling cross-community interaction	#engagement events	15 -20 -30	1
Podcast series for project providing interview-based discussions on several topics	#downloads (in total)	800 - 1100 - 1300	n.a.

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Table 2: LUMEN KPIs

8. Conclusion & Outlook

The communication and dissemination strategy and activities described in this deliverable aim to enhance the overall awareness of LUMEN and foster engagement with LUMEN outcomes in all four scientific communities represented in the project. D8.2 serves as the conceptual foundation of all communication and dissemination activities in LUMEN. According to the evaluation and monitoring framework, the strategy, as well as the effectiveness and efficiency of the described actions, will be evaluated and, if necessary, adjusted in D8.3 “Update plan for communication and dissemination” due in M19.

Beyond this, future updates to the communication and dissemination plan (D8.3 and D8.4) will further elaborate on aspects that require discussion at a later stage. This includes topics such as communication and dissemination activities concerning specific Key Exploitable Results (KERs) or dedicated community engagement campaigns.

9. References

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